

Crafting Multimedia Text of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang as the Gift Shop in Palembang

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ABSTRACT: This research presents crafting multimedia text containing information about Griya Kain Tuan kentang as the gift shop in Palembang. The purpose of this research is to find how to craft the multimedia text of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang as the gift shop in Palembang by applying the steps for crafting multimedia text. The writers used the Research and Development method modified by Sukmadinata (2005) to achieve the purpose. The result shows that there are three steps to craft the multimedia text of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang as the gift shop in Palembang. The steps are preliminary study, model development, and final product testing. Based on the result, the multimedia text consists of the profile of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the history of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the kinds of products sold in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the range of prices, and the website or social media.

Keywords: *Crafting, Multimedia Text, Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, Gift Shop*

INTRODUCTION

Becoming the host of the biggest Multi-event, the Asean Games 2018 made Palembang famous nowadays. The success of the Asean Games 2018 made Palembang known as a sports tourism city. Tourism is the activity of humans travelling within their own country or to other countries to visit certain interesting places to relax or other purposes. According to Nasrullah, et al. (2020), tourism is a journey taken by a person from an area of origin to the tourist destination to enjoy recreational activities to fulfill the various desires. When people do travel, they will visit some gift shops. The purpose of tourists to come to the gift shop are to refresh themselves, and to buy gifts for family or colleagues.

One of the gift shops in Palembang is Griya Kain Tuan Kentang where *Jumputan* and other traditional clothes from Palembang are sold. Griya Kain Tuan Kentang as the gift shop is located in Kampung Tuan Kentang Seberang Ulu 1, Palembang. The uniqueness of this gift shop lies in that, besides the tourists can buy the cloth, tourists can also see the process of making *Jumputan* and *Blongsong*. Unfortunately, the information about making *Jumputan* and *Blongsong*

process at Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is rarely known by tourists who come to Palembang city. The information about making *Jumputan* and *Blongsong* processes as the uniqueness of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is also lacking. One of the ways that tourists can find information about Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is by making a marketing multimedia.

Uploading marketing multimedia about the uniqueness of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang on the internet can be an effective way to provide information anytime and anywhere because it can be accessed not only by domestic tourists, but also the international tourists. Marketing multimedia has several advantages because of the combination of visual and audio. It works well in delivering the messages and attracting the viewer's attention. The use of information technology in the form of multimedia can help make the process of delivering information, messages, and materials more enjoyable. When producing marketing multimedia, multimedia text is an essential element of conveying the multimedia message. According to Yahya (2015), there are three forms of most demanding promotions, namely video, photograph, and text.

Information about Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is conveyed through a multimedia text in English, so that the marketing multimedia is not only watched by local tourists but also by foreign tourists. The multimedia text consists of the information about the location, the kinds of souvenirs that is sold by Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, and the information about making *Jumputan* and *Blongsong* process as the uniqueness of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. Because people are more interested in watching videos than reading, the writers want to provide information and introduce Griya Kain Tuan Kentang through video, or multimedia.

METHOD

The writers used the modification of the Research and Development (R&D) method created by Sukmadinata. Sukmadinata (2005) stated that the modified research and development theory consists of three steps. First, "Preliminary study" It is the first step in preparing the

development. There are three stages in this step; Literature Study, Field Survey, Arranged Draft Model. Second “Model Development” There are two stages in this step; Limited Testing and Wider Testing. Third, “Final Testing” It is the step of the testing product.

The Stages of Research

In order to craft multimedia text of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the stages of research was connected to the stages of script development by Friedmann (2014).

Preliminary Study

This stage was product development. Preliminary study was the first step of this research, and consisted of three steps: literature study, field survey, and product drafting. First, the Literature Study was the study about theoretical concepts to develop the product. In this step, the writers did the first stage of script development (Friedmann, 2014). It was background research and investigation. The writers would find out the information about what the elements were that had to be found in the video script (Jakacaping, 2018), and stages of script development (Friedmann, 2014). Then, the writers would find out the information about Griya Kain Tuan Kentang as the references before doing the observation to collect more data about Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. The writers would find out the information through website (<https://griya-kain-tuan-kentang.business.site>) and watching the video of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang on youtube with the title “*Profil KUBE Griya Kain Tuan Kentang Palembang*” (Afriansyah, 2019).

Furthermore, the writers continued to field survey. The field survey was intended to collect data regarding the planning and execution of the development or making a product. The data that had to be collected were: service, atmosphere, history of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*, location, business field, kinds of products sold, best-selling product, specialty of the place, the process of making the product, range of prices, and website or social media.

It was also still in the first stage of script development (Friedmann, 2014). In this step,

the writers did an observation as a technique of collecting data. The data that had been mentioned above had to be collected using an observation technique. Before doing the observation, the writers needed to prepare the observation log. In this technique, the writers did direct observation. The observation took place in *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*, located on *Jl. Aiptu. A. Wahab Kel. Tuan Kentang Kec. Jakabaring*. The observation took around three hours.

Arif (2014) stated that an instrument was needed to collect the data in the observation method. The instruments needed were camera, mobile phone, a pencil, a pen, a book, and a drawing book. The writers prepared a camera to record the video of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*, a sheet of observation log, and a pen to mark a checklist from the observation log. After doing the observation, the writers collected the videos in a folder on flash disc to make the writers easier in find the videos of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*, and typed the observation log in a form of Microsoft Word along with the mark of a checklist to make the writers to read the information.

The last step was arranging the draft model. The Draft Model was intended to carry out the result of the field survey and referred to the basic theories or concepts that were inferred from the result of the literature study. After all the data had been collected and recorded. This step could be found in the second stage of script development (Friedmann, 2014), which includes concept, treatment, and first draft. The writers started the process of writing the video script of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*.

First, the writers made the concept of the video. The concept of the video was marketing multimedia because the writers would like to introduce *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* through video. Therefore, the writers used a persuasive paragraph in writing the script. Martnez (2016) states, "Persuasive paragraph is a paragraph that gives the writer's opinion on the topic and tries to get the reader to agree with it." The persuasive paragraph was supported by the reason and the data, so the writers used the data that had been collected in the field survey as the material of the script.

After that, the writers continued to make the treatment (Friedmann, 2014). The treatment was about the structure or the arrangement of scenes that could be found in the multimedia text. The writers arranged the information of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang into a sequence. The treatment would be the body of the script. The sequential information of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang: the profile of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, history of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, kinds of products sold in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, range of prices, and website or social media.

After writing a treatment into a paragraph, the writers continued to craft the first draft. The writers paid attention to the elements of a video script (Jakacaping, 2018). In the first draft, the writers wrote full script based on the elements of a video script. The full script was included: hook, opening, body, and closing.

Model Development of the Product

Model development consisted of limited testing and wider testing. Limited testing was a test that the writers did to validate the product. The first product draft was given to the people who have knowledge and experience about the product that would be developed, and the product draft would be revised based on the experts' remarks and hints. In limited testing, the writers gave the draft model to three experts. The writers gave the first draft of the multimedia text in the Indonesian language to the head of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang to check the content of the multimedia text. Next, the writers gave the English multimedia text to be checked the grammatical errors in the multimedia text. After getting some remarks and hint from the experts, the writers did the third stage of script development (Friedmann, 2014). It was revision. The writers did the revision of the first draft by writing what parts were that had to be revised in a multimedia text. After writing the remark and hint, the writers rewrote the multimedia text and made sure there was no problem found in the multimedia text.

Next was wider testing, the writers gave the draft model development of multimedia text that had been revised by linguistic expert to correct the grammatical errors, types of paragraphs, and miss typed. Last, the writers gave the multimedia text to the script writer to check the multimedia text. After getting the suggestion, the writers revised it. The result of wider testing would be the final product. The final product was the fourth stage of script development (Friedmann, 2014).

Product Testing and Dissemination

This step was the last step to develop the product. It consisted of final product testing and dissemination. The writers would not do the product testing and dissemination because of the lack of time, cost, and legal aspect. The writers stopped the work until wider testing was conducted and considered the revision of wider testing as the final product.

FINDINGS

The findings were defined into three abstractions they were Preliminary Study (*Studi Pendahuluan*), Model development (*Pengembangan*), and Product Testing and Dissemination (*Pengujian*) (Sukmadinata, 2005). Those three abstractions were linked to the stages of script development (Friedmann, 2014). The first abstraction was Preliminary study (*studi pendahuluan* – Sukmadinata, 2005). The chart described Sukmadinata (2005) and Friedmann (2006) idea:

Chart 1. First Abstraction

Based on the chart of Sukmadinata (2005) “*Studi Pendahuluan*” was implemented into the four steps of Friedmann (2014). They were background research and investigation, concept, treatment and first draft. First, the writers found out the information from background research and investigation focused on location, atmosphere, history, and product. Second, the concept was introducing Griya Kain Tuan Kentang in detail. Third, pitching is a video presentation it is a means of promoting our competence in creating video. A video pitch is a short video that is created to present ourselves to our future employer. Therefore, this step was not done by the writers. Fourth, treatment was the full script. Fifth, the first draft divided the script based on the scene. Sixth, revision was throwing out unnecessary content, correcting the paragraph, and correcting the grammar mistakes. The last, final draft was the script that was ready to be used for creating the video.

The second abstraction was testing the first draft to alter it to become a better product.

Chart 2. Second Abstraction

Based on the chart, the second set consisted of revision. In this step, the writers made some improvements based on the experts' suggestions. In limited testing, the writers revised grammatical mistakes in the English script. In wider testing, the writers did not get any suggestions because the script was already good and ready to be used in creating the video.

Third abstraction by Sukmadinata (2005) was linked to the stages of script development (Friedmann, 2014):

Chart 3. Third Abstraction

In this step, the writers did not apply this step because of the lack of time, money, and skill. Therefore, the writers used the last revision of the script as the final product.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The discussion informed the process of multimedia text crafting. It was based on three stages of Research and Development (Sukmadinata, 2005) that was implemented into six stages of script development as mentioned by Friedmann (2014).

Literature Study and Field Survey

In this step, the writers collected the data regarding the topic. The writers did the first stage of script development (Friedmann, 2014). It was background research and investigation.

Friedmann (2014) stated, “Research can be undertaken in several well-proven ways. You can consult encyclopedias, visit library, or search in the internet”. To fulfill the first stage of crafting multimedia text, the writers read a book entitled “Writing Visual Media” by Friedmann (2014). In this book, the writers found information about the stages of script development. Friedmann (2014) said, “there are seven stages of script development”. The stages of script development are background research and investigation, concept, pitching, treatment, first draft, revision, and final draft.

Investigation, in this step, Friedmann (2014) stated, “To write about the product, it is needed to read manuals through brochures and interview people in the company who are knowledgeable about the product”. In this stage, the writers observed Griya Kain Tuan Kentang by asking Mrs. Vivie, as the manager of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. The writers got some information about Griya Kain Tuan Kentang based on the observation log prepared before doing the observation. The lists of information that were collected by the writers were: service, atmosphere, history of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*, location, business field, kinds of products sold, best-selling product, specialty of the place, range of prices, and website or social media. The information above was essential to craft the multimedia text of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang.

Arranging Draft Model

In this step, the writers arranged the multimedia text regarding the topic of this multimedia text crafting. The writers did three stages of Arranging Draft Model (Friedmann, 2014), which were concept, treatment, and first draft.

Concept

The concept of the script was to introduce Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. It means that the information in the script must be complete and clear. Introducing Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is

needed because the effort of promoting products by Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is not sufficient. It is proven by the lack of information found in the video on youtube. The writers used the data that had been collected in a field survey to support the material of the script.

One, Location of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang which is located in *Kampung Tuan Kentang, Seberang Ulu I, Palembang*. This place is called *Kampung Tuan Kentang* because in the past, there was a rich man who sold potatoes in this place. Therefore, he was called as *Tuan Kentang*. After *Tuan Kentang* died, this place turns into a place that the majority of the people are Palembang traditional cloth craftsmen.

Two, History of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang started from The Regional Government of Palembang City and Bank Indonesia built a gallery to collect the traditional cloth of Palembang. This gallery was meant to collect the material made by local craftsmen. This has been being the center of marketing the product of local craftsmen. It facilitates the visitors or tourists to easily get the best quality of Palembang traditional cloth from the products of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. The gallery was named Griya Kain Tuan Kentang which was inaugurated in 2017. Three, Social media: Facebook and Instagram. Griya Kain Tuan Kentang used facebook and Instagram in introducing the products. The picture of the product is uploaded through those social media. Not only the picture of the product, Griya Kain Tuan Kentang also uploads the picture of the making process in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang.

Four, Products in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang : *Songket, Blongket, Tajung, Jumputan* and any kinds of accessories such as: necklaces, mask, scarfs, table cloth and cushion cover. From those four kinds of Palembang traditional clothes, the most popular clothes is *jumputan* because it can be used both formal and informal event. There are two best-seller products in this gallery namely *Jumputan* with *titik tujuh* motif as the original motif from Palembang city and *Batik Jumputan* as the latest product in this gallery.

Five, Size: S, M, L, XL, XXL. The size of Palembang traditional clothes is various, S for the smallest one and XXL for the biggest one. Sadly, this gallery has not made the clothes for the kids yet. It only provides the clothes for the teenager and adult.

Six, Price of the products: Rp 50,000 - Rp. 2,300,000. The price of the accessories is ranging from Rp 50,000 until Rp 150,000. For the clothes itself, the price is up to Rp 100,000. It is still affordable and reasonable price because the quality of the product is also very good.

Treatment

Friedmann (2006) said “A treatment is about structure or the arrangement of scenes” Structure means the arrangement and relation between the parts of elements. It is also called as the arrangement of scenes that could be found in the script. The arrangement of the scripts as follows: the introduction of Palembang, location of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the history of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the atmosphere, the products sold, best-seller products, size of the products, and price of the products.

One, the writers wrote the introduction of Palembang. It is essential to give the information of Palembang because the location of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang itself is in Palembang. The writers explained about the specialty of Palembang which is called as “Venice from the east” and “sport tourism city” along with the reasons. By adding the information of Palembang as the beginning of the script, it would make the people would like to go to Palembang.

Two, telling the location of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is needed in the script because location is very important and must be put in the video. By telling the specific location, people can easily know where Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is located. Even if the people do not know Palembang yet, they can easily put the location into the maps in their smart phone. The writers explained the complete address of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang and the point of interest of this gallery.

Three, telling the history of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang made the script more informative. Sometimes, there are several people who would like to know about history of the place beside visiting the place. The writers clearly explained the reasons of building this gallery and the date when this gallery is inaugurated.

Four, the atmosphere is also needed to put in the script. A gift shop must have a good atmosphere to make the visitor comfortable. In the script, the writers explained clearly the atmosphere of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang by telling the scent, the lighting, the mirror, and the parking area. By giving the clear explanation of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the people can imagine the situation in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang.

Five, giving the explanation of the products is the most important part because the viewers of the video must be waiting for the products explanation. The writers explained kinds of the products sold in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang completely such as kinds of clothes and kinds of accessories.

Six, besides telling kinds of product sold in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the writers also explained the best-seller products sold in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. There are two best-seller products namely *Jumputan titik tujuh* and *Batik jumputan*. The writers also explained the reasons why those two products be the best-seller products.

Seven, the information of size is also included in the script. It is necessary to give the information to the people, so they can already know that this gallery has various sizes, starting from S as the smallest size to XXL as the biggest size.

Eight, price of the product is very important to be put in the script because it is the second important information that the viewer of the video is looking for. The writers put the price as the last information to keep the viewers watch the video until the end of the video.

First Draft

In this step, the writers started to arrange the information of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang into a good script. The first draft was included the elements of video script (Jakacaping, 2018) which were hook, opening, body, and closing. Here are the explanation of choosing those idea as the elements of the script:

Hook

The hook intends to obtain the viewer's notice at once and retain it. The hook of the multimedia text is telling what the video will explain about what the special thing of the topic. In this case, the writers talked about Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, a gift shop which sold Palembang Traditional Cloth directly from the craftsmen. It was suitable for the hook because that simple sentence will grab viewer's attention in the first minute of the video. Here is the hook:

Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, a souvenir place that sells Palembang traditional cloth directly from the craftsmen.

By telling the special thing of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang which sold the cloth directly from the craftsmen, the viewer will think that the products sold in this gallery must be cheaper than other places because this gallery is the second-hand of the product. In conclusion, the hook is a sentence that can make people curious to watch the video longer.

Opening

Opening conveys beginning the multimedia text from the overview. Here is the opening:

Venice from the east, the popular nickname of Palembang. This nickname is pinned by western people because Palembang is a city which is surrounded by Musi River just like Venice city in Italy which is surrounded by the Grande canal. Palembang is not only well-known as Venice from the East, but Palembang is also well-known as a sports tourism city because Palembang has often been the host of multi-event sports. The proper infrastructure also supports Palembang to be a right place for tourists to visit.

The multimedia concerns marketing multimedia of gift shop in Palembang. In this case, the writers began the opening by telling the general information of Palembang because Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is the gift shop of Palembang traditional cloth. By giving the information of Palembang, it can also invite the viewers to know more about Palembang. In conclusion, opening is a part of telling the general information before telling the specific one.

Body

Body is the main part of the multimedia text. It consists the essential details of the topic. In this case, the writers explained clearly and completely on the information of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. There was no miss important information of this topic. The location, history, service, atmosphere, products, best-seller product, size and the price of the product was clearly described in the body of the script. Here is the body of the script:

Visiting Palembang is not complete if you do not bring Pempek to your hometown. Pempek is the traditional food of Palembang that can be the souvenirs for the visitors, but there are many other souvenirs that is not less interesting than Pempek. One of them is Palembang Traditional Cloth. To get the Palembang traditional cloth, tourists can visit *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*

which is located on Jalan Aiptu A Wahab Tuan Kentang, Seberang Ulu I, Palembang. The location which is not too far from the center of the city with a calm river view is the specialty of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*.

Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is located in a village where the majority of the people are Palembang traditional cloth craftsmen with good quality. Seeing this potential, the Regional Government of Palembang City and Bank Indonesia built a gallery to collect the traditional cloth of Palembang that is made by local craftsmen. The gallery was named *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* which was inaugurated in 2017. The purpose of building this gallery is to make the visitors or tourists are easier to get the best quality of Palembang traditional cloth because the products in *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* will pass the sorting process. Not only accepting the traditional cloth from craftsmen, but *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* also produces its own traditional cloth to be sold. So, don't be doubt about quality.

Griya Kain Tuan Kentang really gives much attention to the comfort of the tourists who come to this gallery. Standard parking space, good service, nice music, and neatly arranged clothes under the warm light from the available lights make tourists feel comfortable to shop here. Not only shopping, tourists can also

see the process of making traditional Palembang cloth here. The clothes that are sold are also very varied, namely *Songket*, *Tajung*, *Blongket* and the most popular one is *Jumputan* cloth. *Jumputan* cloth is the mainstay of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*. It is the most popular cloth because of its unique shape and it is suitable for both formal and casual clothing.

Titik Tujuh motif is one of the best-seller products in this gallery because it is the origin motif from Palembang. The new products released by *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* is equally interesting. The combination of *Jumputan* and *Batik* is the latest product in this gallery that is very unique and much in demand by tourists. In *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*, tourists can find the cloth for teenagers to adults both women and men of various sizes. Starting from S size for the smallest to XXL size for the largest. In addition, *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* also provides accessories such as: necklaces, scarves, and home accessories such as: table cloths. Is it interesting right? The price is also very affordable, ranging from 50,000 to 2.3 million. The cloth that have been purchased will immediately be packaged beautifully using a paper bag with the logo of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* which is very suitable to give to someone at home.

In conclusion, body is the crucial thing in the script because it consists of the main information of the topic.

Closing

Closing is the last element of the script which consists the conclusion of the script. In this case, the writers invited the viewers to come to *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* and buy the product that was mentioned in the body. Here is the closing:

To find out more information of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*, you can directly visit Facebook and Instagram of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*. So, what are you waiting for? Come to *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* and give the Palembang traditional cloth to someone you loved.

By inviting people, the video will be more interactive and fun because the purpose of the video is introducing and promoting *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* to the viewers. In conclusion, closing is a part of telling your purpose of crafting the multimedia text.

Model Development

After writing the draft of multimedia text of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. The next step was model development. There were two steps in model development: limited testing and wider testing. In this step, the writers conducted the third stage of script development (Friedmann, 2014) which was revision because after the product going through the testing process, the writers revised the draft based on the experts' remark and hint.

Revision

In this limited testing stage, the multimedia text was given to three experts to validate the content of multimedia text and the language used within multimedia text.

Content

In the effort of acquiring remark and hint about the validation of information in the script, the writers gave the Indonesian script to Mr. Sofyan (the head of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang). The writers did not get any suggestion to revise and the expert asked to continue to the next step.

Language

The writers handed over the English multimedia text to Mrs. Sri Gustiani (English lecturer of Sriwijaya State Polytechnic). She gave remark and hint regarding to the grammar, the coherence, diction, conjunction and the unity.

Original	Corrected
<p>Venice from the east, the popular nickname of Palembang. This nickname is pinned by western people because Palembang is a city which is surrounded by Musi River just like Venice city in Italy which is surrounded by the Grande canal. Palembang is not only well-known as Venice from the East, but Palembang is also well-known as a</p>	<p>Palembang city has some given-names due its geographical and demographical reasons. It is known as <i>Venice from the East</i> by western people because Palembang is a city which is surrounded by Musi River just like Venice city in Italy which is surrounded by the Grande canal. Palembang is also known as <i>Sport City</i> due to its capacity to host some</p>
<p>sports tourism city because Palembang</p>	<p>multi-event sports both international such</p>

has often been the host of multi-event sports. The proper infrastructure also supports Palembang to be a right place for tourists to visit.

as Sea games 2011, Asean Games 2018, Bowling World Cup 2019, and national like Pekan Olahraga Nasional 2004. In fact, these reasons are supported by proper infrastructure like light rail transit which have turned Palembang into a right place to be visited either by domestic or foreign tourists.

Visiting Palembang is not complete if you do not bring Pempek to your hometown. Pempek is the traditional food of Palembang that can be the souvenirs for the visitors, but there are many other souvenirs that is not less interesting than Pempek. One of them is Palembang Traditional Cloth. To get the Palembang traditional cloth, tourists can visit *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* which is located on Jalan Aiptu A Wahab Tuan Kentang, Seberang Ulu I, Palembang. The location which is not too far from the center of the city with a calm river view is the specialty of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*.

Visiting Palembang is not complete if you do not bring Pempek as souvenirs. Pempek is a fish cake, a traditional food from Palembang that can be souvenirs for the visitors. However, there are many alternatives of traditional items as souvenirs which are as interesting as Pempek. One of them is Palembang traditional cloth. Palembang has some traditional cloth, namely Songket, Tajung, Jumputan, and Blongket. To get the Palembang traditional cloth, tourists can visit *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* which is located on Jalan Aiptu A Wahab Tuan Kentang, Seberang Ulu I, Palembang. The location is not far

from the center of the city with a calm Musi river view as the uniqueness of *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang*

Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is located in a village where the majority of the people are Palembang traditional cloth craftsmen with good quality. Seeing this potential, the Regional Government of Palembang City and Bank Indonesia built a gallery to collect the traditional cloth of Palembang that is made by local craftsmen. The gallery was named *Griya kain Tuan Kentang* which was inaugurated in 2017. The purpose of this gallery is to make the visitors or tourists are easier to get the best quality of Palembang traditional cloth because the products in *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* will pass the sorting process. Not only accepting the traditional cloth from craftsmen, but *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* also produces its own traditional cloth to be sold. So, don't be doubt about quality.

Griya Kain Tuan Kentang is situated in an area in which the majority of the people are qualified Palembang traditional cloth craftsmen. Knowing this potential, the Regional Government of Palembang City and Bank Indonesia provided a support by establishing a gallery to collect and display the local traditional cloth which is made by those local craftsmen. The gallery was named *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* which was inaugurated in 2017. The purpose of this gallery is to help both domestics and foreign visitors or tourists easier to get the best quality of Palembang traditional cloth. All the products in *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* have passed the quality sorting process. This gallery does not only accept traditional cloth from craftsmen, but also produces its own traditional cloth to be sold. Meaning, the gallery functions both as a selling and

	producing place, so
	don't doubt the quality of the products in there.
<p><i>Titik Tujuh</i> motif is one of the best-seller products in this gallery because it is the origin motif from Palembang. The new products released by <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i> is equally interesting. The combination of <i>Jumputan</i> and <i>Batik</i> is the latest product in this gallery that is very unique and highly demand. In <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i>, tourists can find the cloth for teenagers to adults both women and men of various sizes. Starting from S size for the smallest to XXL size for the largest. In addition, <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i> provides accessories such as: necklaces, scarves, and home accessories such as: table cloths. Is it interesting, right? The price is also very affordable, ranging from Rp 50,000 to Rp 2.3 million. The cloth will immediately be packaged beautifully using a paper bag with the logo of <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i> which is very suitable to give to someone at home.</p>	<p><i>Titik Tujuh</i> motif is one of the best-seller products in this gallery due to the original motif. The new products released by <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i> is equally interesting. The combination of <i>Jumputan</i> and <i>Batik</i> is the latest product in this gallery. It is very unique and highly demand. <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i> sells cloth for teenagers to adults both women and men in various sizes. Starting from S size for the smallest to XXL size for the largest. In addition, <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i> provides accessories such as: necklaces, scarves, and also home accessories such as: table cloths and cushion covers. Is it interesting, right? The price is also very affordable and reasonable, ranging from Rp 50,000 to Rp 2.3 million. The cloth that has been purchased will be immediately packaged beautifully using a paper bag with the logo of <i>Griya Kain Tuan</i></p>
	<i>Kentang</i> on it. The paper bag package is very suitable to be given to someone special as a souvenir
<p>To find out more information of <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i>, you can directly visit Facebook and Instagram of <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i>. So what are you waiting for? Come to <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i> and give the Palembang traditional cloth to someone you loved</p>	<p>To find further information of <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i>, you can directly visit Facebook and Instagram of <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i>. So what are you waiting for? Come to <i>Griya Kain Tuan Kentang</i> and have some Palembang traditional cloth to be given to your beloved ones.</p>

Two was Wider Testing. After limited testing, the writers went on the next testing. It was wider testing. Last expert was Mr. Malkon (script writer of TVRI Palembang). The writers gave the script to Mr. Malkon in order to ask for suggestion and comments. Mr. Malkon stated that the arrangement of the content is good. There is hook to grab people attention, opening body and closing. The script is ready to be used as the script of the video *Griya Kain Tuan Kentang* in order

to introduce Griya Kain Tuan Kentang.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The writers concluded that in crafting multimedia text of Griya Kain Tuan Kentang, the writers used steps of Research and Development modified by Sukmadinata (2005). The steps were preliminary study, development of the product, and final product testing. In Preliminary Study, this step was linked to the idea of script writing by Friedmann (2014). The writers followed three procedures in Preliminary step. First, literature study, the writers collected the data and information about script writing, and articles about Griya Kain Tuan Kentang. Second, field study, the writers did an interview and observation in Griya Kain Tuan Kentang in order to collect the data needed in the model draft of the product. After the data were complete, the writers craft the first draft of multimedia text.

In Development of Product, the writers did two testings to make the multimedia text developed, there are limited testing, and wider testing. In limited testing, the writers gave the product to experts, and asked their comment, suggestion, and correction in aspects of content, script writing, and linguistics. After revision, the writers did wider testing to develop the product. In wider testing, the writers focused on multimedia text, so the writers gave the second draft to experts, and crafted a final product of multimedia text based on the experts' comment, suggestion, and correction.

In Final Product Testing, the writers stopped to develop the multimedia text and considered the result from wider testing as the final result due to lack of time, fund, skill and legality.

The writers would like to suggest the future researchers to conduct dissemination to improve this research be further developed.

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